

Influence of plant growth regulating chemicals on physiology of bhendi under moisture stress

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Abstract

Drought or moisture stress reduces growth and yield of various crops by decreasing chlorophyll pigments, photosynthetic rate, stomatal conductance as well as transpiration rates. Under such water limited conditions, the productivity of the crop can be improved by foliar spray of plant growth regulating chemicals. In the present study, split plot design was employed with moisture stress as main plot (M_0 – No stress, M_1 – Moisture stress at vegetative stage, M_2 – Moisture stress at reproductive stage) and foliar spray of plant growth regulating chemicals as sub plot (S_1 – Control, S_2 – Proline (50 mM), S_3 – KCl (1%), S_4 – Glycine betaine (50 mM), S_5 – Ascorbic acid (100 ppm), S_6 – Salicylic acid (100 ppm)) in three replicates. Among the physiological parameters observed, the maximum Relative Water Content (RWC) (89.8%) was observed with glycine betaine (50 mM) treatment at 40 Days. While the highest Chlorophyll Stability Index (CSI) (88.2%) was observed in proline (50 mM) treatment at 60 Days. Similarly, the Membrane Stability Index (MSI) (82.1%) was maximum with proline (50 mM) treatment at 40 Days. With respect to biochemical parameters, the higher leaf proline content of $315.9 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ was observed in proline (50 mM) treatment at 80 Days. The maximum leaf soluble protein content (17.1 mg g^{-1}). While, the catalase activity was maximum ($7.9 \mu\text{g H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) with proline (50 mM) as well as ascorbic acid (100 ppm) at 60 Days.

Keywords: Moisture stress, Plant growth regulating chemicals, Glycine betaine, Proline

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1. Introduction

Bhendi (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) Moench, popularly known as lady's finger or okra. It is the only vegetable crop of significance in the Malvaceae family. The genus *Abelmoschus* originated in India (Masters et al., 1875). India being largest producer (67.1%) in Bhendi, followed by Nigeria (15.4%) and Sudan (9.3%). It is an annual, often cross pollinated crop usually propagated through seeds. It is cultivated for its immature pods or green non-fibrous fruits containing round seeds and eaten as vegetable. In the preparation of gur or brown sugar, the roots and stem of bhendi is used for clarification of sugarcane juice (Chauhan, 1972). The oil content of bhendi seed is about 20-40%. Various scientists reported that seed oil of okra can be used as an alternate source of edible oil. Due to its high fiber and mucilage content, bhendi can be used to cure gastric problems and treat digestive issues (Gemedé et al., 2015).

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Bhendi is highly sensitive to drought, low temperature and flood conditions. Among various stresses, drought is one among the utmost adverse factors affecting plant growth and productivity and considered as serious threat for sustainable crop production in the circumstance on altering climate (Anjum et al., 2011). Under water limited conditions, the productivity of the crop can be improved by adopting suitable management practices especially at critical stages of crop growth. One such management practice is the use of certain chemicals which facilitate maintenance of internal water balance at an optimal level (Kramer and Boyer, 1995).

Exogenous application of proline is known to induce abiotic stress tolerance in plants, since, proline protect protein structure and cell membranes from damage, and thereby reduce enzyme denaturation. Maggio et al. (2002) reported that proline accumulation under stress can also act as a regulatory and signaling molecule in activating a variety of responses.

Glycine betaine, an important quaternary ammonium compound is considered to be one of the most effective osmoprotectant against abiotic stress (Dawood, 2018). It is reported that, glycine betaine is the only solute accumulated in higher plants subjected to osmotic stress, satisfies other solute requirements (Gorham et al., 2000).

Ascorbic acid, a non-enzymatic complex, plays important role like protection against Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) that are formed from photosynthetic and respiratory processes (Naz et al., 2016). Foliar spray of ascorbic acid can alleviate oxidative damage occurred due to drought in okra (Amin et al., 2009).

Salicylic acid (SA) plays an important role in plants in abiotic stress tolerance (Raskin, 1992). It acts as an important signaling molecule in plants and has different effect on tolerance to abiotic stress.

Potassium (K) is one of the essential macronutrient required by the plants. It serves as a primary osmoticum under stressful environments. Potassium fertilization increased nitrate assimilation and dry matter production under drought (Zhang et al., 2014). Exogenous application of potassium can alleviate drought induced negative effects on plant by regulating protein synthesis and osmoregulation (Maathuis and Sanders, 1996).

2. Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted in the "C" block of Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai. The farm is located at 9°54" N latitude and 78°54" E longitude at an elevation of 147 m above Mean Sea Level (MSL). The soil type is sandy clay loam soil with available soil moisture at field capacity and permanent wilting point was 23.1% and 9.6% respectively. Split plot design was used with moisture stress as main plot (M_0 – No stress, M_1 – Moisture stress at vegetative stage, M_2 – Moisture stress at reproductive stage) and foliar spray of plant growth regulating chemicals as sub plot (S_1 – Control, S_2 – Proline (50 mM), S_3 – KCl (1%), S_4 – Glycine betaine (50 mM), S_5 – Ascorbic acid (100 ppm), S_6 – Salicylic acid (100 ppm)) in three replicates. Water stress was imposed by withholding irrigation at vegetative and reproductive stages. Water stress plots were irrigated at 50% depletion of available soil moisture. The available soil moisture was estimated gravimetrically before each irrigation by taking and pooling samples at 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm soil layers (Dastane, 1967). The amount of water at each irrigation was sufficient to raise the soil moisture content of top 0-30 cm layer back to field capacity. The following observations were taken on 40, 60 and 80 days after sowing.

2.1. Relative water content (RWC)

The RWC was estimated according to Barrs and Weatherley (1962) and calculated by using following formula and expressed as percent.

$$RWC = [(Fresh\ weight - Dry\ weight) / (Turgid\ weight - Dry\ weight)] \times 100$$

2.2. Chlorophyll stability index (CSI)

CSI was determined by utilizing following protocol by adopting the method of (Murphy, 1962) and expressed in percentage.

2.3. Membrane stability index (MSI)

MSI was determined by utilizing following protocol by adopting the method of Premachandra et al. (1990) as modified by Sairam (1994) and expressed in percentage.

2.4. Leaf soluble protein

Soluble protein content in the leaf was estimated by the procedure described by (Lowry et al., 1951) using Folin Ciocalteu reagent and expressed as mg g⁻¹ fresh weight.

2.5. Leaf proline

The proline content of the leaf was estimated through the protocol given by Bates *et al.* (1973) and expressed in mg g^{-1} .

2.6. Catalase activity

Catalase activity was determined by following titration method using potassium permanganate (Gopalachari, 1963) expressed as $\mu\text{g H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

3. Results and discussion

With regard to RWC, the interaction effect of moisture stress and plant growth regulating chemicals responded significantly. Among different treatment combinations, the treatment combination of M_2 – Moisture stress at reproductive stage with S_4 – Glycine betaine (50 mM) showed highest RWC of 93.2% at 40 Days (Table 1). Since, glycine betaine offers osmoprotection, thereby protecting cell organelles from dehydration through regulating water potential equilibrium and maintaining turgor pressure in the cell (Kaya *et al.*, 2013). This report was proved by the use of glycine betaine in wheat cultivar where the RWC improved under drought conditions (Salama *et al.*, 2015).

Treatment	Relative water content (%)											
	40 Days				60 Days				80 Days			
	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean
S ₁	90.3	73.2	89.9	84.5	81.3	65.9	68.6	71.9	77.2	62.6	65.2	68.3
S ₂	93.2	81.4	92.6	89.0	83.8	73.2	81.0	79.4	79.6	69.6	77.0	75.4
S ₃	92.7	80.5	91.7	88.3	83.4	72.5	79.1	78.3	79.2	68.8	75.2	74.4
S ₄	94.3	81.9	93.2	89.8	84.9	74.0	82.1	80.3	80.6	70.3	78.0	76.3
S ₅	90.9	78.2	90.8	86.6	81.8	70.3	77.6	76.6	77.7	66.8	73.7	72.7
S ₆	92.6	80.5	91.2	88.1	83.3	72.5	80.5	78.8	79.1	68.8	76.5	74.8
Mean	92.3	79.3	91.6		83.1	71.4	78.2		78.9	67.8	74.3	
	SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)	
M	0.42		1.18		0.78		2.17		0.31		0.85	
S	0.69		1.43		0.81		1.66		0.99		2.04	
M x S	1.18		2.53		1.51		3.37		1.61		3.33	

The values of CSI was found to be increasing up to 60 Days, after that started declining at both moisture stress and plant growth regulating chemicals. Among different treatment combinations, the treatment combination of M_2 – Moisture stress at reproductive stage with S_2 – Proline (50 mM) showed highest CSI of 87.5% at 60 Days (Table 2). This findings were supported by foliar application of osmolytes like proline in safflower in stabilizing the chlorophyll content (Janmohammadi *et al.*, 2017).

The MSI differs for each treatments and get decreased with increment in age of bhendi. Among different treatments with plant growth regulating chemicals, foliar spray of S_2 – Proline (50 mM) recorded maximum MSI of 82.1, 70.2 and 55.6% at 40, 60 and 80 Days respectively (Table 3). Membrane stability will be lost or started to decline with increase in stress level, which is due to electrolyte leakage from damaged tissues (Farooq *et al.*, 2008). This electrolyte leakage is due to increased lipid peroxidation of biomembrane. Under

Table 2: Effect of plant growth regulating chemicals on chlorophyll stability index (%) in bhendi hybrid CO₄ under moisture stress conditions

Treatment	Chlorophyll stability index (%)											
	40 Days				60 Days				80 Days			
	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean
S ₁	83.2	58.8	82.9	75.0	90.2	64.6	75.1	76.6	77.8	54.9	63.8	65.5
S ₂	86.3	76.7	85.3	82.7	92.9	84.3	87.5	88.2	79.0	71.7	74.4	75.0
S ₃	85.7	71.3	85.0	80.7	92.2	78.5	87.2	86.0	78.4	66.7	74.1	73.1
S ₄	84.7	70.5	84.2	79.8	91.2	77.6	86.4	85.1	77.5	65.9	73.5	72.3
S ₅	83.9	65.5	82.7	77.4	90.9	72.1	84.8	82.6	76.7	61.3	72.1	70.0
S ₆	84.7	72.6	84.7	80.7	91.1	79.9	87.0	86.0	77.5	67.9	73.9	73.1
Mean	84.7	69.2	84.1		91.4	76.2	84.7		77.8	64.7	72.0	
	SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)	
M	0.88		2.43		1.12		3.11		0.74		2.06	
S	1.48		3.02		1.48		3.03		1.00		2.05	
M x S	2.49		5.33		2.60		5.66		1.76		3.81	

Table 3: Effect of plant growth regulating chemicals on membrane stability index (%) in bhendi hybrid CO₄ under moisture stress conditions

Treatment	Membrane stability index (%)											
	40 Days				60 Days				80 Days			
	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean	M ₀	M ₁	M ₂	Mean
S ₁	78.9	68.5	76.4	74.6	72.6	65.4	58.1	65.4	54.7	49.2	48.3	50.7
S ₂	86.0	77.4	83.0	82.1	78.6	70.7	62.9	70.7	59.1	53.2	54.4	55.6
S ₃	81.8	73.6	81.7	79.0	76.8	69.1	61.4	69.1	58.3	52.4	51.3	54.0
S ₄	80.5	72.5	78.1	77.0	76.9	69.2	61.5	69.2	57.8	52.0	51.0	53.6
S ₅	76.2	71.0	76.2	74.5	74.4	67.0	59.6	67.0	56.0	50.4	49.2	51.9
S ₆	85.0	76.5	85.2	82.2	77.4	69.7	61.9	69.7	57.9	52.1	53.2	54.4
Mean	81.4	73.3	80.1		76.1	68.5	60.9		57.3	51.6	51.2	
	SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)		SEd		CD (P:0.05)	
M	0.94		2.62		0.56		1.54		0.41		1.14	
S	0.95		1.94		0.85		1.74		0.56		1.15	
M x S	NS				NS				NS			

Figure 1: Effect of plant growth regulating chemicals on leaf soluble protein content (mg g⁻¹) of bhendi hybrid CO₄ under moisture stress

Figure 2: Effect of plant growth regulating chemicals on leaf proline content (µg g⁻¹) of bhendi hybrid CO₄ under moisture stress

present study the foliar spray of proline (50 mM) responded positively to moisture stress, where it maintained the stability of the membrane through reduced electrolyte leakage. Lower the leakage percentage indicates higher membrane stability.

The leaf soluble protein content mostly represents the RuBisCO activity in plants. The protein content reduced to nearly 56% under drought which might be due to either protein degradation or inhibition of synthesis. In okra, drought reduced soluble protein to nearly 22.4% (Raza et al., 2013). Among different treatment combinations, the treatment combination of M₂ – Moisture stress at reproductive stage with S₂ – Proline (50 mM) showed highest leaf soluble protein content of 16.7 mg g⁻¹ at 60 Days (Figure 1). The positive role of proline in maintaining soluble protein content in leaf tissue of some plants like maize where exogenous proline application maintained homeostasis under stress condition (De Freitas et al., 2018).

Proline accumulated during stress in higher plants. The amount of proline increased upon ageing of bhendi and found to be maximum at 80 Days. Among different treatment combinations, the treatment

Figure 3: Effect of plant growth regulating chemicals on catalase activity ($\mu\text{g H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) of Bhendi Hybrid CO₄ under moisture stress

combination of M₁ – Moisture stress at vegetative stage with S₂ – Proline (50 mM) recorded highest leaf proline content of 291.8, 321.6 and 337.9 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ at 40, 60 and 80 Days respectively (Figure 2). This results was supported by Merwad *et al.* (2018), where there was increased accumulation of proline was observed with exogenous proline application which served as a resistance index. Moreover, it enhanced the growth and uptake of mineral ions from water limited soil, maintained water status, enhanced activity of antioxidant enzymes like catalase, peroxidase and superoxide dismutase. Similar results were observed in faba bean treated with proline (Taie *et al.*, 2013a). Foliar spray of proline mitigated drought stress through decreasing the rate photoinhibition and increased proline content scavenging the ROS production in leaves of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Moustakas *et al.*, 2011). However, some reports provided by Taie *et al.* (2013), where proline spray combined with sea water had no significant effect in enhancement of endogenous proline.

Plants regulate various defense mechanisms to overcome the destructive effects of stress, which includes production of antioxidants like catalase, ascorbate peroxidase, super oxide dismutase and peroxidase in order to scavenge ROS, thereby preventing lipid peroxidation. Among these enzymes, catalase is the most active enzyme, since it play a major role in scavenging the oxidant H₂O₂ present in peroxisomes which will be converted to water and molecular oxygen with the activity of catalase. Among different treatment combinations, the treatment combination of M₂ – Moisture stress at reproductive stage with S₂ – Proline (50 mM) showed highest catalase activity of 9.65 $\mu\text{g H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 40 Days (Figure 3). Similarly, proline enhances catalase activity in basil plants (Agami *et al.*, 2016), cowpea (Merwad *et al.*, 2018) under water limited conditions and also in maize (De Freitas *et al.*, 2018), chilli (Butt *et al.*, 2016) under saline conditions.

References

- Agami, R., Medani, R., Abd El-Mola I. and Taha, R. (2016). Exogenous application with plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) or proline induces stress tolerance in basil plants (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) exposed to water stress. *Int J Environ Agri Res.* 2(5), 78.
- Amin, B., Mahlegah, G., Mahmood, H.M.R. and Hossein, M. (2009). Evaluation of interaction effect of drought stress with ascorbate and salicylic acid on some of physiological and biochemical parameters in okra (*Hibiscus esculentus* L.). *Res. J. Biol. Sci.* 4, 380-387.
- Anjum, S.A., Xie, X.Y., Wang, L.C., Saleem, M.F., Man, C. and Lei, W. (2011). Morphological, physiological and biochemical responses of plants to drought stress. *African Journal of Agricultural Research.* 6 (9), 2026-2032.
- Barrs, H. and Weatherley, P. (1962). A re-examination of the relative turgidity technique for estimating water deficits in leaves. *Australian Journal of Biological Sciences.* 15(3), 413-428.

- Bates, L.S., Waldren, R.P. and Teare, I. (1973). Rapid determination of free proline for water-stress studies. *Plant and Soil*. 39(1), 205-207.
- Butt, M., Ayyub, C., Amjad, M. and Ahmad, R. (2016). "Proline application enhances growth of chilli by improving physiological and biochemical attributes under salt stress. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 53 (1).
- Chauhan, D. (1972). *Vegetable Production in India* Pub. by Ram Prasad and Sons. Agra.
- Dastane, N. (1967). *A practical manual for water use research in agriculture*. Navabharat Prakashan Publications, Pona (India). 5-6.
- Dawood, M.G. (2018). Improving drought tolerance of quinoa plant by foliar treatment of trehalose. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*. 19(5), 245-254.
- De Freitas, P.A.F., De Souza Miranda, R., Marques, E.C., Prisco, J.T. and Gomes-Filho, E. (2018). Salt tolerance induced by exogenous proline in maize is related to low oxidative damage and favorable ionic homeostasis. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*. 37(3), 911-924.
- Farooq, M., Basra, S., Wahid, A., Cheema, Z., Cheema, M. and Khaliq, A. (2008). Physiological role of exogenously applied glycinebetaine to improve drought tolerance in fine grain aromatic rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*. 194(5), 325-333.
- Gemed, H.F., Ratta, N., Haki, G.D., Woldegiorgis, A.Z. and Beyene, F. (2015). Nutritional quality and health benefits of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*): A review. *J. Food Proc. Technol*. 6(6), 1-6.
- Gopalachari, N. (1963). Changes in the activities of certain oxidizing enzymes during germination and seedling development of *Phaseolus mungo* and *Sorghum vulgare*. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*. 1(2), 98-100.
- Gorham, J., Jokinen, K., Malik, M. and Khan, I. (2000). Glycine betaine treatment improves cotton yields in field trials in Pakistan. *Proc. World Cotton Res. Conf. II*. Athens, Greece.
- Janmohammadi, M., Asadi, F., Sabaghnia, N., Abbasi, A., Nouraein, M. and Shekari, F. (2017). The effects of foliar feeding of compatible organic solutes on agronomic traits of safflower. *Agriculture (Pol'nohospodárstvo)*. 63(4), 128-141.
- Kaya, C., Sönmez, O., Aydemir, S. and DÝkÝIÝtaþ, M. (2013). Mitigation effects of glycinebetaine on oxidative stress and some key growth parameters of maize exposed to salt stress. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*. 37(2), 188-194.
- Kramer, P.J. and Boyer, J.S. (1995). *Water Relations of Plants and Soils*. Academic Press.
- Lowry, O.H., Rosebrough, N.J., Farr, A.L. and Randall, R.J. (1951). Protein measurement with the folin phenol reagent. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 193, 265-275.
- Maathuis, F.J. and Sanders, D. (1996). Mechanisms of potassium absorption by higher plant roots. *Physiologia Plantarum*. 96(1), 158-168.
- Maggio, A., Miyazaki, S., Veronese, P., Fujita, T., Ibeas, J.I., Damsz, B., Narasimhan, M.L., Hasegawa, P.M., Joly, R.J. and Bressan, R.A. (2002). Does proline accumulation play an active role in stress-induced growth reduction?. *The Plant Journal*. 31(6), 699-712.
- Masters, M.T., Eichler, A.W., Endlicher, S., Fenzl, E., von Martius, C.F.P. and Urban, I. (1875). *Aristolochiaceae: Oldenbourg*.
- Merwad, A.R.M., Desoky, E.S.M. and Rady, M.M. (2018). Response of water deficit-stressed *Vigna unguiculata* performances to silicon, proline or methionine foliar application. *Scientia Horticulturae*. 228, 132-144.
- Moustakas, M., Sperdouli, I., Kouna, T., Antonopoulou, C.I. and Therios, I. (2011). "Exogenous proline induces soluble sugar accumulation and alleviates drought stress effects on photosystem II functioning of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaves. *Plant Growth Regulation*. 65(2), 315.
- Murphy, K. (1962). Modifications of the technique for determination of chlorophyll stability index in relation to studies of drought resistance in rice. *Curr. Sci*. 31, 470-471.
- Naz, H., Akram, N.A. and Ashraf, M. (2016). Impact of ascorbic acid on growth and some physiological attributes of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) plants under water-deficit conditions. *Pak J Bot*. 48(3), 877-883.

- Premachandra, G., Saneoka, H. and Ogata, S. (1990). Cell membrane stability, an indicator of drought tolerance, as affected by applied nitrogen in soyabean. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*. 115(1), 63-66.
- Raskin, I. (1992). Role of salicylic acid in plants. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*. 43(1), 439-463.
- Raza, S.H., Shafiq, F., Chaudhary, M. and Khan, I. (2013). Seed invigoration with water, ascorbic and salicylic acid stimulates development and biochemical characters of okra (*Ablemoschus esculentus*) under normal and saline conditions. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*. 15(3).
- Sairam, R. (1994). Effect of moisture-stress on physiological activities of two contrasting wheat genotypes. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*. 32, 594-594.
- Salama, K.H., Mansour, M.M. and Al-Malawi, H.A. (2015). Glycinebetaine priming improves salt tolerance of wheat. *Biologia*. 70(10), 1334-1339.
- Taie, H., Abdelhamid, M., Dawood, M. and Nassar, R. (2013). Pre-sowing seed treatment with proline improves some physiological, biochemical and anatomical attributes of faba bean plants under sea water stress. *J Appl Sci Res*. 9(4), 2853-2867.
- Zhang, L., Gao, M., Li, S., Alva, A.K. and Ashraf, M. (2014). Potassium fertilization mitigates the adverse effects of drought on selected *Zea mays* cultivars. *Turkish Journal of Botany*. 38(4), 713-723.

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